

Flexibility, Content and Perceived Ease of Use Towards SVOD Subscription Intention Mediated by Perceived Price

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Abstract:- The pandemic has caused some limitations on mobility and changed everyone's lifestyle, including on how to enjoy videos such as movies, television series, sport events and else. This study aims to boost the subscribers of video on demand service by examining the effects of flexibility, content and perceived ease of use mediated by perceived price. This study used 188 data obtained from an online questionnaire which the respondents are those who live in Jakarta, Depok, Tangerang and Bekasi. The research used quantitative methods with the Partial Least Square (PLS) - Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique with the Smart PLS 3.0 program. This study proved that flexibility, content and perceived ease of use significantly affected subscription intention. However, found that perceived price negatively affected subscription intention. Yet, perceived price was proven to be able to mediate content and perceived ease of use in a positive and significant way towards the subscription intention.

Keywords:- Flexibility, Content, Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Price, Subscription Based Video on Demand (SVOD), Subscription Intention, Competitive Mediation.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, internet has become a need which is necessary for Indonesians to carry out their daily activities. It can be seen from the rapid growth of internet users every year. It reached 204.7 million users as of February 2022. There was an increase in the number of users by 54.25% compared to 2018 (Annur, 2022). A survey conducted by the Association of Indonesian Internet Service Providers in 2020 showed that the distribution of internet users in Indonesia was uneven and concentrated in Java (APJII, 2021). This data was also supported by the Speedtest Global Index report for the third quarter of 2021 which showed that 4 of the top 5 cities with the best internet speed and quality were in Java, namely Jakarta (24.31 Mbps), Bekasi (23.55 Mbps), Tangerang (23.37 Mbps) and Depok (22.74 Mbps) (Maulida, 2022)

On average, each user spent 8 hours 36 minutes using the internet and 2 hours 50 minutes for watching broadcasts or streaming (We are Social, 2022). Commercial video streaming services Over-The-Top is also called Subscription Video on Demand (SVOD), defined as content aggregators and creators that provided unrestricted access to the video repository for a

specified period of time and a specified subscription fee. This video streaming platforms were accessible from various devices such as smartphones, tablets, laptops, personal computers, and smart televisions (Menon, 2022).

In Indonesia there are various kinds of SVOD providers including Disney+, Netflix, Amazon Prime, Hulu, Viu, WeTV and Vidio.com which is local platform owned by PT Elang Mahkota Teknologi Tbk. The growth rate of SVOD market share in Indonesia is expected to continue to increase by 13.7% annually, with profits reaching USD 468.20 million in 2026 (Statista, 2022). The positive growth of the SVOD market share in Indonesia is on the contrary with the growth of Vidio.com's market share which has decreased at the end of 2021 by 1%. This decline phenomenon did not occur in other SVOD providers such as Netflix, Viu, Disney+ and Amazon Prime which showed increase during the COVID-19 pandemic.

There has been numerous research on SVOD subscription intention conducted in many countries using different theories such as Uses and Gratification Theory (UGT), Theory of Reasoned Actions (TRA) and the most often used so far Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) dan Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

Theory of Planned Behavior was first introduced by Icek Ajzen in 1985. It was developed from Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA). The development carried out by adding the perceived behavioral control (PBC) construct. PBC is translated as a person's belief in controlling himself by considering the supporting and inhibiting factors that they perceived to carry out a behavior (Amanu, 2019). TPB determined attitudes toward behavior, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control, which led to subscription intention of a product (Hsu, Chang, & Yansritakul, 2017).

Based on the previous literature review concluded by Gu and Wu (2019), individual attitudes are influenced by their experiences, choices and expectations. Subjective norms have a significant effect on determining behavioral intention. And perceived behavioral control is an individual evaluation that considers various aspects that are known.

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was also developed from TRA which was introduced in 1986. Its development lies in the constructs of perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU), which affect attitudes toward using and generate actual system usage. PEOU is the level of consumer confidence that the use of technology services is easy to understand and it is not difficult to interact using technology (Hubert et al, 2019). PU is defined as the ability to facilitate use, increase efficiency and frequency of use (Wu et al, 2017). The TAM conceptual framework demonstrated that PU and PEOU could predict behavior towards using a technology and lead to actual use.

TAM and TPB has been widely used and developed to study SVOD and validate the statement that a person's level of acceptance of technological developments can predict their intention in subscribing to SVOD services (Lestari & Soesanto, 2020; Lee, et al, 2019; Camilleri & Falzon, 2020).

B. Flexibility

Nowadays, mobility freedom is one of the needs to have in deciding how and when to watch a video (Dasgupta and Grover, 2019). Menon (2022) stated that one of the advantages of SVOD services was to be able to store and download video so that people could enjoy it at their desired time. Mulla (2022) stated that users were pleased if they could rate or recommend a video that they have watched to others. Flexibility was defined as the ability to choose which device to use to access the SVOD platform and how long they could access it (Massad, 2018). Hence, the term of flexibility in this study refers to the choice of devices and time to use the service and the ability to interact in SVOD platform.

The dimensions of flexibility are accessing SVOD directly from television, downloading videos on SVOD and having the ability to provide ratings or recommend videos to other users (Dasgupta and Grover (2019), Mulla (2022) and Nagaraj, et al. al (2021).

C. Content

Most studies stated content as the strongest factor in determining which SVOD platform consumers would choose. Nagaraj et al (2021) mentioned that users consider the availability of content from various countries and the quality of High-Definition images as reasons for choosing SVOD platform. Mulla (2022) in his research stated that in this digital era, consumers can easily find the type of content that suits their tastes and lifestyle, such as sports shows, documentaries, television series, news or educational and comedy shows. Dasgupta and Grover (2019) also stated the same thing, SVOD providers can present interesting content in various genres that users can connect with as to create engagement. Innovations on how to visualize the content such as using visual graphics or special display effects must be considered as well. Above all, good storyline must also be in mind (Menon, 2022). Then, content referred to the availability of choices of genres, channels, country of origin and quality of video shows on SVOD platform.

D. Perceived ease of use

Winata and Permana (2020) concluded that perceived ease of use as indication for someone to use new technology which will reduce their efforts to learn it compared to the old technology. Users would not be confused in understanding the features in the SVOD platform (Mulla, 2022). Perceived ease of use is defined as the ease which users feel in finding what they are looking for within the platform, such as using an interface that is effortless to understand and can quickly describe its functions.

E. Perceived price

According to Auditya and Hidayat (2021), perceived price is the total costs which are sacrificed and spent to get a product or service and consumers would get satisfaction from knowing the price decency. In Calvo-Porrall and Lévy-Mangin (2017), perceived price refers to the perceived cost as a consumer's evaluation of the affordability of a product. Palomba (2020) stated that perceived price was a consumer's review about the price worth compared to the perceived benefits.

The level of data consumption used to access SVOD services is one of the considerations for some users, because in the end the costs spent were subscriptions fee and internet data charge (Dasgupta and Grover, 2019). Koul, et al. (2020) found that most users choose to subscribe to SVOD services on an annual basis, compared to monthly, quarterly and per biannually. Then the meaning of this variable is the perception of the fairness of the overall costs spent by the consumers with the return benefits they got from SVOD services.

F. Subscription Intention

Subscription intention in this research refers to purchase intention. Purchase intention said to be the most important indicator in predicting consumer behavior. Subscription interest was the intention or possibility to register as a customer because of trust and confidence in the product offered (Sabrina et al, 2022).

Subscription intention was buying an access to a platform or service provider for a certain period of time (Nagaraj et al, 2021). Due to mobilization has been increasing nowadays, people developed a need to access SVOD services so they would not be left behind from what was happening globally (Dasgupta and Grover, 2019). In addition to these needs, intention to subscribe to SVOD services could also be measured by knowing that there was a tendency to subscribe to SVOD services in the near future (Leowarin & Thanasuta, 2021) and whether there was some curiosity to find which SVOD services that suit the user's tastes (Palomba, 2021). Yet, the subscription intention in this study is defined as the desire to access VOD services for a certain time in the near future.

III. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Based on the literature reviews and previous research above, below is the conceptual framework proposed in this study:

Fig 1. Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis testing aims to examine the relationship between variables and analyze the similarities or differences that might be found. The hypothesis proposed for this study is as follows:

- H1: Flexibility has positive significant influence on subscription intention.
- H2: Content has positive significant influence on subscription intention.
- H3: Content has positive significant influence on perceived price.
- H4: Perceived ease of use has positive significant influence on perceived price.
- H5: Perceived ease of use has positive significant influence on subscription intention
- H6: Perceived price has positive significant influence on subscription intention.
- H7: Content has positive significant influence on subscription intention mediated by perceived price.
- H8: Perceived ease of use has positive significant influence on subscription intention mediated by perceived price.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This research is quantitative research to determine causal relationships. For this research, the population studied was individuals who subscribed and made decisions to subscribe to SVOD services themselves who lived in Jakarta, Depok, Tangerang and Bekasi. Sampling technique used is purposive sampling method by using an online questionnaire distributed via WhatsApp. The questionnaire was using a Likert scale for each proposed indicator. The data collected were 267 respondents, but the number of valid data that could be used for this research was 188 respondents. This study used the Partial Least Square (PLS) - Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) technique with SmartPLS 3.0 software.

V. RESULTS DAN DISCUSSION

The characteristics of the respondents in this study were based on gender, age and residence. From 188 valid respondent data, there was a balanced composition between male (50%) and female (50%). For the age group, it was known that there were 27 respondents aged 15-20 years (14.4%), 103 respondent of aged 21-34 years (54.8%), 50 respondents of aged 35-49 years (26.6 %), and 8 people of aged 50-64 years (4.2%). It shows that the research respondents were dominated by the age of 21 - 34 years. As for the residence, respondents were dominated by 67 people (35.6%) from Jakarta, 45 people (23.9%) from Tangerang, 48 people (25.6%) from Bekasi and 28 people (14.9%).

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
Flexibility	F1	0,763	0,834	0,832	0,803
	F2	0,809			
	F3	0,757			
Content	K1	0,8	0,82	0,794	0,784
	K2	0,738			
	K3	0,753			
Perceived ease of use	P1	0,694	0,962	0,743	0,75
	P2	0,87			
	P3	0,811			
Perceived price	H1	0,834	0,817	0,837	0,825
	H2	0,79			
	H3	0,717			
Subscription intention	M1	0,739	0,799	0,812	0,868
	M2	0,809			
	M3	0,761			

Table 1. Construct Validity dan Discriminant Validity

The examination of Composite Reliability, Cronbach's Alpha dan Average Variance Extracted aims to test the reliability of the instrument in a research model. If all latent variables have composite reliability or Cronbach's alpha values, it means that the constructs are reliable or the questionnaire used as a tool in this study was reliable or consistent.

The results of the Heterotrait-Monotrait test showed no value more than 0.9 so that it can be concluded that the research model proposed from the five variables above was valid.

Variable	Flexibility	Content	Perceived ease of use	Perceived Price	Subscription Intention
Flexibility	0,724				
Content	0,648	0,618			
Perceived ease of use	0,518	0,762	0,733		
Perceived Price	0,824	0,689	0,893	0,734	
Subscription intention	0,811	0,881	0,57	0,749	0,817

Table 2. Heterotrait-Monotrait

A model will be considered fit if it has an SRMR value below 0.10 or 0.08. The Normed Fit Index value produces a

value of 0 to 1, a good NFI value is a value close to 1. The NFI value is obtained from 1 minus Chi-square.

<i>Fit Measures</i>	<i>Saturated Model</i>	<i>Estimated Model</i>
SRMR	0.06	0.06
d_ULS	2,83	2,83
d_G	1.73	1.73
Chi-Square	581.31	581.31
NFI	0.82	0.82

Table 3. *Fit Measures*

From the table above it can be seen that the proposed model is considerably fit. Meanwhile, the Variance Inflation Factor value of the model does not exceed 5, so it can be concluded that there was no multicollinearity in the model.

Variable	Perceived Price	Subscription Intention
Flexibility		0,163
Content	0,147	0,144
Perceived ease of use	0,122	0,151
Perceived price		0,160

Table 4. *F-square*

There was a moderate effect size value with an F-Square value between 0.15 and 0.35 in H1, H5 and H6. As for the small effect size value with the criteria of the F-Square value being in the range of 0.02 to 0.15, were found in H2, H3 and H4. From the results of the F-square value above, there was no negligible effect because there was no F Square value <0.02.

Variable	R²	Q²
Perceived price	0,764	0,436
Subscription intention	0,836	0,571

Table 5. *R-square dan Q-square*

R² value ≥ 0.67 indicates that the model has a strong variable, while a Q² value that is greater than 0 indicates that the model has predictive relevance.

Hipotesis	Original Sample	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values	Keterangan
[H1] Flexibility → Subscription Intention	0,383	0,372	2,763	0,003	Positive - Significant
[H2] Content → Subscription Intention	0,273	0,237	3,642	0,001	Positive - Significant
[H3] Content → Perceived Price	0,366	0,323	3,459	0	Positive - Significant
[H4] Perceived ease of use → Perceived price	0,329	0,364	2,905	0,004	Positive - Significant
[H5] Perceived ease of use → Subscription Intention	0,284	0,479	3,792	0,002	Positive - Significant
[H6] Perceived price → Subscription Intention	-0,394	0,358	4,693	0,002	Negative - Significant

Table 6. Direct effect

Hypothesis	Original Sample	Standard Deviation	T Statistics	P Values	Remark
[H7] Content → Perceived price → Subscription intention	0,437	0,318	3,264	0,001	Positive - Significant
[H8] Perceived ease of use → Perceived price → Subscription Intention	0,464	0,325	3,489	0,003	Positive - Significant

Table 7. Indirect Effect

Hypothesis one has a T-statistic value of 2.763, an original sample value of 0.383 and a P-Values of 0.003. So, the results of the study indicate that flexibility affected SVOD subscription intention positively and significantly. The first hypothesis was also supported by Leowarin & Thanasuta (2021), Mulla (2022) and Chen (2019). Menon (2022) stated that one of the advantages of SVOD services was being able to save and download video shows to be enjoyed at the desired time and controlled on how often they wanted to watch it.

Having control in the hands of users to determine which device they would use to access SVOD services at the time they wanted and at the rhythm they wanted were important factors that users considered because of their desire not to be left behind. The ability to rate a video was much favored by the younger generation because they would indirectly take a role in determining shows that would be recommended by service providers to other users.

The results of the second hypothesis also showed positive and significant results. This result was aligned with previous research conducted by Kwon and Kim (2020), Tefertiller (2020) Zahara et al (2022) and Yusuf et al (2019). Palomba (2021) in his research mentioned that the frustration caused by lack of show to watch could be a reason for customers to switch to other services.

Based on a survey conducted by Pwc annually since 2013 to 2019 of people in the United States, consistent results were obtained, namely SVOD service users are motivated by the availability of a portfolio of content that could be watched in determining the right service. They were in search of the ideal combination of the video content options available in the platform with their need of content criteria. The booming of content from other countries that were previously dominated by *Hollywood*, such as *Money Heist* (Spain) and *Squid Game* (South Korea) on Netflix had given a new color in terms of quality and variety of content. Meanwhile, the existence of educational content or documentary series on SVOD services could broaden the users' horizon on what was happening in other parts of the country, which previously were only shown in certain media and not many provided that kind of content. Quality content could be achieved by selecting competent actors, good storylines and amusing acting so that it would attract the intention to watch (Ponggeng and Mulia, 2020).

So, it can be summarized that the more suitable the available content choices and the better the quality of the content offered, the more attractive consumers would be to subscribe to an SVOD service because consumers could find new attracting contents for them to enjoy.

Content had significant positive effect on perceived price. The third hypothesis was also accepted because the T-statistic value was 3.459, the original sample value was 0.366 and the P values was 0.000. This proved that the better the choice and quality of the content, the better the consumers perceived the subscription price. Gupta and Singharia (2021) advised over-the-top service providers to provide content offering packages that vary and adapt to the interests and buying behavior of their users. Lee, et al, (2019) suggested that SVOD service provider company managers to prioritize perceived price to build a customer base whom enjoyed the content of their services.

As discussed earlier in the Pwc report, SVOD subscribers in the United States felt that the subscription fee they were charged was reasonable and worthed with the variety of content they could watch. With the extensive availability of a variety of content that could be enjoyed, customers were increasingly accepting subscription prices for the SVOD services. It could be acknowledged, because the core business of SVOD services was as a paid content provider, which the the selling point was the content. The better the consumers assessed the contents presented by a provider, the better the price the perceived.

The fourth hypothesis, the direct effect between perceived ease of use on perceived price, also entitled for a positive significant result. The T-statistic value was 2.905, the

original sample value was 0.329 and the P values was 0.004. The ability to maximize the use of SVOD services in an easy and concise manner also influenced the perceived price. This result supported the previous research conducted by Tefertiller (2020) and Palomba (2021).

Numerous changes experienced by people caused by the empowerment of information technology. It helped them in their daily activities or transactions. The convenience, less complicated and direct connectedness felt by consumers in using SVOD services affected their perceived price. The more they did not find it difficult to use the service, the better the perceived price.

The fifth hypothesis showed positive and significant results with a T-statistic value of 3.792, an original sample value of 0.284 and a P value of 0.002. It supported the previous research by Tefertiller (2020), Lee, et al (2018), Moslehpour, et al. (2018), Basuki, et al. (2022) and Palomba (2021). Tefertiller (2020) stated that the easier it was to use the SVOD service, the more benefits users could experience from using it. This statement was also Moslehpour et al (2018) and Basuki et al (2022), that perceived ease of use had a positive and significant effect on subscription intention. However, there were contradictory research results in the studies of Wei et al (2018) and Chen (2019) which showed that perceived ease of use did not affect purchase intention.

Elsafty and Boghdady (2017) suggested in their research that system developers in SVOD services should focus on the efficiency and ease of use from a consumer's perspective, so as to design and develop an easy to access and to use platform. In the era of the widespread use of technology in many aspects of daily life, it was encouraged that all SVOD service providers to continuously develop their services in order to consistently maintain or increase the convenience benefits the consumers embraced.

Previous research had shown significant relationship between perceived price and subscription intention. While the results of the sixth hypothesis in this study showed a negative but significant result. The T-statistic value is 4.693, the original sample value is -0.394 and the P values are 0.002. It was interpreted as the worse the consumer's perception of price, the higher the interest in subscribing to SVOD services. Meanwhile, the research of Suhud, et al (2022), Calvo-Porrall and Lévy-Mangin (2017) and Permatasari and Kuswadi (2017) obtained positive values for perceived price but not significantly influence the subscription intention. The results of this study needed to be followed up by reconsidering the dimensions used to measure perceived price and whether there was any probable cause by the characteristics of respondents who were dominated by the age group of 21-34 years (54.8%) and Jakarta as the place of residence. In summary, the poor perceived price actually led to consumers' desire to subscribe to a SVOD service.

The seventh hypothesis can also be accepted with a T-statistic value of 3.264, an original sample value of 0.437 and a P value of 0.001. It described that the perceived subscription fee the consumer felt to enjoy contents on SVOD services

influenced their intention in subscribing to the platform. This was supported by previous studies by Park (2017) and McKenzie (2019).

The consumers interest in buying a product or service must consider the principle of fairness of the monetary value and perceived benefits. Thus, the price perceived by consumers to watch a content -as the main function of VOD services- was able to influence subscription intention. Each VOD service provider make available different origins and types of content. One of the special features of SVOD services is the presence of original content that only exists in particular service provider because each also produces contents of their own and are not shared with other service providers. Likewise, the technology used by the provider in producing good quality content image will affect the internet data consumption. In the end, consumers will weigh and compare the internet data fees and subscription fees that they spend to get the rights to watch content on an SVOD platform as factors that affect their intention.

The eighth hypothesis could be accepted because the T-statistic value was 3.489, the original sample value was 0.464 and the P values are 0.003. It reflected the perceived subscription fee in order to be able to feel the ease of use of SVOD influenced the subscription intention. The previous research by Zahara et al (2022) and Udoakpan & Tengeh (2020) concluded the same.

The utilization of information technology had driven the consumer behaviors to change that they demand to get what they want swiftly, less hassle and at a minimal cost compared to the last few decades. The internet, which was a rare and expensive product back then, had become a public facility thanks to the many innovations that have taken place.

Based on the said technology developments, consumers are becoming more aware of the financial value of a product that uses technology with the convenience benefits provided by this technology. The more reasonable the price perceived by consumers for the ease of understanding and connecting to an SVOD service, the more they are willing to subscribe. Consumers expect that there will be ease of use in return which worth the subscription fees and internet data fees they spend in using SVOD.

This study used perceived price as a mediating variable for content and perceived ease of use. Based on the results of indirect hypothesis testing, perceived price was able to perform the ability as a mediating variable between content and perceived ease of use on subscription intention. However, the result of the direct effect result between perceived price and subscription intention was not able to support the proposed sixth hypothesis. Hence, the type of mediation analysis obtained in this study was competitive mediation.

The study showed that the negative value obtained from the sixth hypothesis (perceived price towards subscription intention) was in the opposite direction to the value obtained in the seventh and eight hypotheses. The sixth hypothesis had a negative value, while the seventh and eighth hypotheses

earned a positive value. This opposite direction of values indicated that there was a possibility of other mediating variable needed to complete the framework in this study.

VI. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Based on research that has been done by testing eight hypotheses in the conceptual framework, found there were seven hypotheses which are accepted. Whereas the sixth hypothesis was rejected.

Therefore, several managerial suggestions were concluded that could be applied in Vidio.com to increase the subscribers. First, there should be an interactive feature available, to accommodate the customers to rate the video they have watched so that other customers can find out whether or not a video is worth to watch. This is critical to consider because the participation of consumers in giving their opinions will be able to influence other consumers to follow or want to watch the recommended videos in Vidio.com.

Second, it is better to extend the variety of contents provided on the service by adding social related videos such as documentary and environmental campaigns which takes place in other countries. It is due to contents are the core business of SVOD, so it will be crucial if providers do not innovate continuously to keep up with changes in consumer preferences that are increasingly aware and show better empathy values than before towards social issues around the world.

Third, it should make the platform easier to connect with other electronic devices besides mobile phones, such as Smart TVs. Currently there are several SVOD providers that have included built-in SVOD features in the menu provided by the Smart TV without the need to download the platform first. It enables the customers to access SVOD easier.

VII. LIMITATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

There were only four variables used in the framework which are flexibility, content, perceived ease of use and perceived price to test the influence towards subscription intention. Perceived price as the mediation variable has not demonstrated maximum effects. Thus, it is suggested that the future research to add other independent variable or mediation variable such as lifestyle, e-wom and service credibility to complete the framework in this study.

Future research could also develop broaden research by stretching the population and samples, not limited to Jakarta, Depok, Tangerang and Bekasi. Moreover, the future research needs to look deeper into the effect of perceived price on SVOD subscription intention among millenials to examine their behavior in determining the intention to or not to subscribe an SVOD platform. Considering the generation Z characters are different from their previous generations, the next research should be conducted by quantitative research combined with interviews in order to provide a complete and thorough visibility.

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